

**EXTRACTION OF
WOOD FINES
FROM
POST-CONSUMER
FIBREBOARD
(DRY PROCESS)**

**PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET**

Contributing to the EU's circular bioeconomy, reintegrating post-consumer fibreboard into production helps optimise wood use, extend product lifecycles, stores carbon and reduce dependence on virgin wood.

Post-consumer fibreboard chips to wood fines

APPLICATIONS

Dieffenbacher's dry process downsizes post-consumer fibreboard chips into a defined particle size and removes coatings. It can be integrated into particleboard plants. The material is afterwards screened into:

- Oversize, recirculated for further milling.
- Fines, used in particleboard surfaces.
- Dust, used in Bioblocks, the modular construction units developed in the project.

ACHIEVEMENTS

- Advanced to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6, converting around 22 tonnes of post-consumer fibreboard into secondary fines.
- Produced fines that meet particle size requirements for particleboard surface layers and validated their use in this application.
- Separated coatings into a dedicated stream.
- Demonstrated that the remaining dust can be used in Bioblocks, the modular construction units developed in the EcoReFibre project.

NEXT STEPS

- Optimise process parameters and plant layouts.
- Refine key settings, such as rotation speed and screen mesh size, to maximise output quality and quantity for downstream production.

PARTNERS

DIEFFENBACHER
MOVE FORWARD. TOGETHER.

SONAE ARAUCO
Taking wood further

CONTACTS

DIEFFENBACHER GMBH MASCHINEN- UND ANLAGENBAU

Germany

MICHAEL RUPP

Head of Business Unit Recycling

[dieffenbacher.com](https://www.dieffenbacher.com)

michael.rupp@dieffenbacher.com

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Department of Forest Biomaterials and Technology - Division of Wood Science and Technology | Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos

Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

[slu.se](https://www.slu.se)

[More information:](#)

[EcoReFibre on LinkedIn](#)

[.ecorefibre.eu](https://www.ecorefibre.eu)

This document reflects the authors' views only and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Photo credits: Dieffenbacher, InnovaWood.
Layout: Fovéa création.